

SKETCH-DRIVEN POLICY SYNTHESIS: EXTENDING EMBODIED CONTROL THROUGH VISUAL ABSTRACTIONS

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ABSTRACT

This paper explores the potential of using hand-drawn sketches as an interface for robot embodied control, addressing a gap in human-robot interaction (HRI) for non-English speakers and individuals with special needs. It investigates whether sketches, without predefined patterns, can be used for robot control. A survey with 15 prompts was distributed to gather diverse sketches, which were then analyzed using a state-of-the-art multimodal Large Language Model (LLM), GPT-4V. Findings reveal that while sketches can effectively bridge language barriers and simplify task descriptions, the lack of predetermined patterns reduces accuracy. The success of sketch interpretation is influenced by the visual complexity of tasks, with an average accuracy of 39.2%, and accuracy per task varying from 0% to 100%. This study highlights both the potential and limitations of using LLMs for sketch-driven policy synthesis and suggests that a hybrid approach combining verbal and non-verbal communication could yield optimal results in HRI. The code and survey answers are available at <https://github.com/bgrochowski/SDPS>.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the evolving landscape of human-robot interaction (HRI) and robot learning, the need for diverse and inclusive communication methods has become increasingly apparent. While the novel "Code as Policies" project demonstrated the feasibility of natural language-driven robot embodied control [1], it also uncovered a critical gap: not everyone communicates effectively through spoken or written English. This is particularly true for individuals with special needs, such as those on the autism spectrum, who may find visual forms of expression, like drawing, more intuitive and accessible [2].

This research addresses this gap by exploring an alternative form of robot control interface: sketches. Previous studies in this area have demonstrated the potential of using hand-drawn maps [3] and sketches for robot navigation [4][5][6]. However, these approaches often relied on predefined schemes and rules, where each stroke is analysed independently and interpreted as a specific instruction. This limits the utility of these approaches to professional contexts.

This project aims to answer the question "can hand-drawn sketches without predetermined patterns be used for robot embodied control?", particularly by leveraging multimodal Large Language Models (LLMs) to interpret sketches without any preset assumptions or rules. This approach not only democratizes robot control, making it accessible to a wider range of users, but also introduces a level of flexibility and freedom of expression previously unattainable in robot policy synthesis.

In pursuit of this approach, a methodical study was conducted to build a comprehensive sketch database. This was achieved by creating and distributing a survey with 15 distinct prompts, encouraging participants to draw example sketches. These sketches were then meticulously analyzed using a multimodal LLM. The evaluation of these sketches was conducted through a combined strategy, harnessing both

the analytical capabilities of the LLM and thorough manual inspection.

This paper details the journey in developing a system that can intuitively translate unstructured sketches into actionable robot policies. By doing so, it aims not only to extend the capabilities of embodied control in robots but also to open new avenues for inclusive and adaptable human-robot interactions, especially for those who might find traditional methods of communication challenging.

2. METHODOLOGY

This study commenced with a survey aimed at gathering a diverse dataset of sketches. 10 participants took part in the survey, along with own contribution (serving as example for LLM), to generate sketches in response to 15 distinct prompts. These prompts were designed to cover various scenarios, including 8 involving a tabletop manipulator, 2 for drawing on a whiteboard, 3 involving a mobile robot, and 2 other tasks. Their design also employed varying level of difficulty and abstraction. Complete list of tasks can be found in Appendix A.

Notably, the participants were not frequent sketchers, with an average sketching frequency of 3.3 out of 10 (STD = 2.05), ensuring a desired non-professional approach. The sketches varied significantly in many ways, from tablet-drawn, to pen-drawn sketches on paper and drawn in an image editing program like MS Paint.

The core of the methodology revolved around the analysis of these sketches. The chosen multimodal LLM for the analysis was GPT-4V (Vision), as the state-of-the-art technology [7]. Each sketch was processed with 2 examples from within the same category to generate a high-level abstract robot policy code, considering robot's visual environment. This method does not produce executable code, but as proven by [1], employing hierarchical code generation can achieve working code. This project focuses on analysing the correctness of sketch interpretation.

To evaluate the effectiveness of the LLM in interpreting and translating sketches into robot policies, the LLM’s output was assessed for its accuracy and relevance by plain GPT-4 LLM, mimicking the actor-critic framework. Subsequently, manual inspections were done to ensure a comprehensive understanding of the sketches and their corresponding policy codes.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Upon examination of the gained sketches, various aspects become apparent. Sketch-driven policy synthesis can clear many ambiguities present in verbally communicated robot task description. Figure 1 shows how a sketch explains what could someone have in mind by stating ”vertical line”

Figure 1: Different interpretations of ”vertical line” as a desired robot output.

Other visible effect upon examination of the sketches are ”task pre-simplification”, meaning that part of the work to be done by a LLM in verbally communicated instruction is done by the user in sketch-driven control. For example, a sort instruction in text would employ a sorting function in the code, whereas in the sketch the user carries down the task of sorting the elements.

The initial results of this study, utilizing GPT-4 in conjunction with manual supervision, indicate varying degrees of task interpretation accuracy. The evaluation focused on determining if the task intention was clearly discernable from the generated (and sometimes incomplete) code.

Notably, the accuracy of task interpretation varied significantly across different tasks. The highest accuracy achieved was 100% for the task ”Draw a simple star pattern on the whiteboard,” indicating a clear and unambiguous interpretation by the LLM. Conversely, the most challenging task was ”Go in a square around the stool as many times as needed, check each step if there is a coca cola can, only stop moving when you see it,” which recorded an accuracy of 0%. This suggests that more complex, abstract multi-step instructions pose significant challenges for current LLM interpretation capabilities. Feedback from the survey participants also mentioned that this task posed a challenge for them to represent such a complex task in a sketch.

The biggest challenge for the LLM in the project was the lack of predetermined patterns. This was expected to be a difficult part, as this is the key of the research question. GPT-4V achieved mixed generalization results, but struggled in non 2 dimensional tasks, or drawing letters, where in both of these cases the variance of expressing the tasks among users was significant. This is shown in Figure 2

Figure 2: Different expressions for creating a vertical pyramid.

The average accuracy across all tasks was found to be 39.2%, underscoring the nascent stage of this technology in interpreting diverse and complex human instructions through sketches. These results highlight the potential and limitations of using LLMs for sketch-driven policy synthesis in robotics, pointing towards the need for further refinement and development in the field. The study’s ongoing nature suggests that as the model is fine-tuned and more data is fed into the system, improvements can be expected in task interpretation accuracy.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This research provides insightful revelations about the use of sketches for robot policy synthesis. While sketches offer a viable alternative to traditional methods, the absence of predetermined patterns poses a challenge, impacting accuracy levels. However, this approach effectively eliminates language barriers, making robot control more accessible across diverse user demographics.

The findings indicate that the success of sketch-driven policy synthesis is closely linked to the visual complexity of the task, particularly in terms of spatial orientation. Tasks with less visual complexity tended to yield higher accuracy in interpretation.

For future work, comparing different multimodal Large Language Models (LLMs) in the context of robot policy code generation and evaluation could provide deeper insights. Additionally, implementing learning algorithms to recognize a user’s specific sketching patterns could pave the way for more personalized control mechanisms, although increasing API usage cost per instruction due to larger prompt.

Considering a hybrid approach that combines verbal and non-verbal methods of embodied control may offer the most promising results. Such a combination could leverage the strengths of both communication modes, potentially enhancing the overall efficiency and user experience in human-robot interaction.

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- Arrange blocks in a square pattern on the table
 - Sort colored boxes into respective containers
 - Draw a simple star pattern on the whiteboard
 - Stack boxes in a vertical pyramid
 - Arrange the boxes in a diagonal
 - Navigate through a simple slalom on the floor
 - Move a red-colored object to another bowl
 - Move the series of boxes from horizontal to vertical line
 - Follow the path drawn on the ground
 - Move an apple to another bowl
 - Write 'robot' on the whiteboard
 - Sort the objects based on size
 - Go in a square around the stool as many times as needed, check each step if there is a coca cola can, only stop moving when you see it

A. LIST OF ROBOT TASKS

- Move the orange box to the lower right corner
- Move the red book from the left shelf to the right one